

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 72

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 72

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 72:0 <i>A Psalm</i> of Solomon.</p>	
<p>Psa. 72:1 Give the King “Your judgments, O God, And ^bYour righteousness to the</p>	<p>Psa. 72:1 לְשִׁלְמָה אֱלֹהִים מִשְׁפָּטֶיךָ לְמֶלֶךְ תֵּן וְצַדִּיקְתֶּךָ לְבֶן-מֶלֶךְ : ² יִדְּיִן עַמֶּךָ</p>
<p>King’s son. ² ¹May ²he “judge Your people with righteousness</p>	<p>בְּצַדִּיק וְעֲנִיִּיךָ בְּמִשְׁפָּט : ³ יִשְׂאוּ הַרְיָם שְׁלוֹם לָעָם</p>
<p>And ^{3b}Your afflicted with justice. ³ ¹Let the mountains bring ^{2a}peace to the people,</p>	<p>וְגִבְעוֹת בְּצַדִּיקָה : ⁴ יִשְׁפֹּט עֲנִיִּי-עָם יוֹשִׁיעַ לְבְנֵי אֲבִיוֹן וַיִּדְכָּא עוֹשֵׂק : ⁵ יִירָאוּךָ עַם-</p>
<p>And the hills, in righteousness. ⁴ ¹May he “vindicate the ²afflicted of the people, Save the children of the needy And crush the oppressor.</p>	<p>שְׂמֵשׁ וְלְבְנֵי יָרֵחַ דָּוָר דוֹרִים : ⁶ יִרַד כַּמָּטֵר עַל-גֵּז כְּרִבִיבִים זְרִיף אֲרָץ : ⁷ יַפְרֹחַ-בְּיָמָיו צַדִּיק וְרֹב שְׁלוֹם עַד-בְּלֵי יָרֵחַ : ⁸ וַיִּירָד מַיִם עַד-יָם וּמִנְהַר עַד-</p>
<p>Psa. 72:5 ¹Let them fear You “while the sun <i>endures</i>, And ²as long as the moon, throughout all generations. ⁶ ¹May he come down “like rain upon the mown grass, Like ^bshowers that water the earth. ⁷ In his days ¹may the “righteous flourish, And ^babundance of peace till the moon is no more.</p>	<p>אֲפֹסֵי-אֲרָץ : ⁹ לְפָנָיו יִכְרַעוּ צִיִּים וְאֵיזְבוּ עָפָר יִלְחָכוּ : ¹⁰ מִלְכֵי תַרְשִׁישׁ וְאֵיִם מִנְחָה יִשִּׁיבוּ מִלְכֵי שָׁבָא וְסֹבָא אֲשַׁכְּר יִקְרִיבוּ : ¹¹ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּ-</p>
<p>Psa. 72:8 May he also rule “from sea to sea And from the River to the ends of the earth. ⁹ ¹Let “the nomads of the desert ^bbow before him, And his enemies ‘lick the dust.</p>	

¹⁰ ¹Let the kings of ^aTarshish and of the ^{2b}islands bring presents;

The kings of ^cSheba and ^dSeba ^eoffer ³gifts.

¹¹ ¹And let all ^akings bow down before him,

All ^bnations serve him.

Psa. 72:12 For he will ^adeliver the needy when he cries for help,

The ¹afflicted also, and him who has no helper.

¹³ He will have ^acompassion on the poor and needy,

And the ¹lives of the needy he will save.

¹⁴ He will ^{1a}rescue their ²life from oppression and violence,

And their blood will be ^bprecious in his sight;

¹⁵ So may he live, and may the ^agold of Sheba be given to him;

And let ¹them pray for him continually;

Let ¹them bless him all day long.

Psa. 72:16 May there be abundance of grain in the earth on top of the mountains;

Its fruit will wave like *the cedars of* ^aLebanon;

And may those from the city flourish like ^bvegetation of the earth.

¹⁷ May his ^aname endure forever;

May his name ¹increase ^{2b}as long as the sun *shines*;

And let *men* ^cbless themselves by him;

^dLet all nations call him blessed.

לוֹ כָּל-מְלָכִים כָּל-גּוֹיִם

יַעֲבֹדוּהוּ : כִּי-יֵצֵיל אֲבִיוֹן ¹²

מִשׁוּעֵ אֶעֱנֵי וְאִין-עֶזֶר לוֹ : ¹³

יָחַס עַל-דָּל וְאֲבִיוֹן וְנַפְשׁוֹת

אֲבִיוֹנִים יוֹשִׁיעַ : ¹⁴ מִתְּרוֹךְ

וּמִחָמַס יִגְאָל נַפְשָׁם וַיִּיקַר

דָּמָם בְּעֵינָיו : ¹⁵ וַיְחִי וַיִּתֵּן-לוֹ

מִזֶּהָב שֶׁבֶא וַיְתַפְּלֵל בְּעַדּוֹ

תָּמִיד כָּל-הַיּוֹם יְבָרְכֵנָהוּ : ¹⁶

יְהִי כַפֶּת־בַּר אֶבְרָרִץ בְּרֹאשׁ

הָרִים יִרְעֶשׂ כָּל-בְּנוֹן פְּרִיֹו

וַיֵּצִיצוּ מִעִיר כְּעֶשֶׂב הָאָרֶץ :

¹⁷ יְהִי שִׁמּוֹ לְעוֹלָם לְפָנַי-

שְׁמִשׁ יִנִּין [יִנּוֹן] שִׁמּוֹ

וַיִּתְּבָרְכוּ בּוֹ כָּל-גּוֹיִם

יִאֲשְׁרוּהוּ : ¹⁸ בְּרוּךְ אִתְּנָה

אֱלֹהִים אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל עֲשֵׂה

נִפְלְאוֹת לְבָדּוֹ : ¹⁹ וּבְרוּךְ אֱלֹהֵי

שֵׁם כְּבוֹדוֹ לְעוֹלָם וַיִּמְלֵא

כְּבוֹדוֹ אֶת-כָּל הָאָרֶץ אֱמֵן |

וְאֱמֵן : ²⁰ כָּל־יְהוּדָה תִּפְלֹת דָּוִד

בֶּן-יִשִׁי :

Psa. 72:18 ^aBlessed be the LORD
God, the God of Israel,
Who alone ^bworks wonders.
¹⁹ And blessed be His ^aglorious name
forever;
And may the whole ^bearth be filled
with His glory.
^cAmen, and Amen.

Psa. 72:20 The prayers of David
the son of Jesse are ended.

References

Psalm 72:1

^a1 Kin 3:9; 1 Chr 22:13

^bPs 24:5

Psalm 72:2

¹Or *He* will judge

²Many of the pronouns in this Psalm may be rendered *He* since the typical reference is to the Messiah

³Or *Your humble*

^aIs 9:7; 11:2-5; 32:1

^bPs 82:3

Psalm 72:3

¹Or *The mountains will bring*

²Or *prosperity*

^aIs 2:4; 9:5, 6; Mic 4:3, 4; Zech 9:10

Psalm 72:4

¹Or *He will vindicate*

²Or *humble*

^aIs 11:4

Psalm 72:5

¹Or *They will fear*

²Lit *before the moon*

^aPs 72:17; 89:36, 37

Psalm 72:6

¹Or *He will come down*

^aDeut 32:2; 2 Sam 23:4; Hos 6:3

^bPs 65:10

Psalm 72:7

¹Or *the righteous will flourish*

^aPs 92:12

^bIs 2:4

Psalm 72:8

^aEx 23:31; Zech 9:10

Psalm 72:9

¹Or *The nomads...will bow*

^aPs 74:14; Is 23:13

^bPs 22:29

^cIs 49:23; Mic 7:17

Psalm 72:10

¹Or *The kings...will bring*

²Or *coastlands*

³Or *tribute*

^{a2}Chr 9:21; Ps 48:7

^bPs 97:1; Is 42:4, 10; Zeph 2:11

^{c1}Kin 10:1; Job 6:19; Is 60:6

^dGen 10:7; Is 43:3

^ePs 45:12; 68:29

Psalm 72:11

¹Or *All kings will bow down*

^aPs 138:4; Is 49:23

^bPs 86:9

Psalm 72:12

¹Or *humble*

^aJob 29:12; Ps 72:4

Psalm 72:13

¹Lit *souls*

^aProv 19:17; 28:8

Psalm 72:14

¹Lit *redeem*

²Lit *soul*

^aPs 69:18

^{b1}Sam 26:21; Ps 116:15

Psalm 72:15

¹Lit *him*

^aIs 60:6

Psalm 72:16

^aPs 104:16

^bJob 5:25

Psalm 72:17

¹Or *sprout forth*

²Lit *before the sun*

^aEx 3:15; Ps 135:13

^bPs 89:36

^cGen 12:3; 22:18

^dLuke 1:48

Psalm 72:18

^{a1} Chr 29:10; Ps 41:13; 89:52; 106:48

^bEx 15:11; Job 5:9; Ps 77:14; 86:10; 136:4

Psalm 72:19

^aNeh 9:5; Ps 96:8

^bNum 14:21

^cPs 41:13

Targum

Psa. 72:1 Composed by Solomon, uttered in prophecy. O God, give your just rulings to the King Messiah, and your righteousness to the son of King David. ² Let him judge your people in righteousness, and your poor with just rulings. ³ The inhabitants of the mountains will lift up peace for the house of Israel, and the hills in purity. ⁴ He will judge the poor of the people, he will redeem the sons of the lowly, and he will purge away the oppressor. ⁵ They will fear you at the rising of the sun, and they will pray in your presence before the light of the moon for all generations. ⁶ He will descend like the favorable rain on the grass that is cut because of locusts, like the drops of late rain that drip on the grass of the earth. ⁷ The righteous will increase in his days, and peace abound, until those who worship the moon are destroyed. ⁸ And he will rule from the bank of the Great Sea to the bank of the Great Sea, and from the Euphrates to the ends of the earth. ⁹ The governors will bow down before him, and his enemies will lick the dust. ¹⁰ The kings of Tarsus and the islands of the ocean sea will bring back tribute; the kings of Sheba and Seba will offer gifts. ¹¹ And all kings will do homage to him; all the Gentiles will submit to him. ¹² For he will deliver the lowly who seeks favor, and the poor who have no helper. ¹³ He will pity the indigent and lowly, and he will redeem the souls of the lowly. ¹⁴ From duress and from extortion he will redeem their souls, and their blood will be precious in his presence. ¹⁵ And he will live and give to him some of the gold that they brought to him from Sheba, and he will pray for him always; every day he will bless him. ¹⁶ Let there be the support of bread in the land on the top of the mountains; its fruit will quiver like Lebanon, and they will blossom from the city of Jerusalem like the grass of the earth. ¹⁷ May his name be invoked for ever; and before the sun came to be his name was determined; so all the peoples will be blessed by his merit, and they shall speak well of him. ¹⁸ Blessed is the LORD God, God of Israel, who works great wonders by himself. ¹⁹ And blessed is his glorious name forever, and let the whole earth be filled with his glorious splendor. Amen and amen. ²⁰ The prayers of David son of Jesse are complete. --

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is the last one of the Second book of Psalms. It is also the last Psalm dedicated to events in King David's life. The sage Radak said that David was near death when he wrote this Psalm. The day of its creation was a triumphant day of celebration. David had crowned Solomon to replace him as the King of Israel. There was an unprecedented celebration that day. As David reviewed the events of his life, he realized that many of his cherished plans for creating a perfect society based on the Torah remain unfulfilled. David charged Solomon to be his spiritual heir with creating a utopian world order predicated on Divine righteousness and justice.

Verse three

An additional task has been given to the LORD's people. The LORD himself sanctified this task, and that is

שִׁפְטֵי “is used attributively when applied to God himself as to his character. The Lord is the just judge (2 Chr 12:6; Ps 11:7; Jer 12:1; Lam 1:18) even to the utmost degree as the judge of all the earth (Deut 32:4; Ps 119:137; Isa 5:16). Therefore his standards, his judgments set out in his word are righteous (Ps 119:144, 160, 172). Being everlasting, they are the confidence of his people and will not fall. God's hate of sin and love of righteousness (45:7 [H 8]) express his essential righteousness. Therefore righteousness and judgment are the habitation (“foundation” NASB, NIV) of God's throne, i.e. they always characterize his actions (97:2).”¹

¹ The Wordbook of the Old Testament electronic verse from Accordance Bible software. 2023.

This factor will finally complete the state founded upon the LORD's Torah and enable faithful Shalom (peace). This factor is charity. A society based on the Torah needs to take care of one another. A conscientious sense of duty toward the LORD and voluntary service to one's brothers is necessary.

This verse is written metaphorically by David.

Metaphorical translation - But the mountains bring peace to the people and the hills through a sense of duty.

Spiritual translation – May the people have peace through their duty to the LORD and their brothers and sisters.

Verse six

In verse five, David said the people should revere the LORD before the King. The King and princes of the nation should come upon the people as rain from the sky. The word used for princes is the same term used for clouds. The idea is that the rain is a much-needed gift from the LORD. Israel was a land where water was always sparse. The King and Princes were to help the people to remain dedicated to the ways of the LORD and His Torah.

Metaphorical translation - May he descend like rain upon the mown meadow, as showers of rain, a waterer of the earth.

Spiritual translation – May the nation's King and princes help the people grow and prosper by following the ways of the Torah.

Verse seven

David hoped that Solomon and future kings would not be indiscriminate in their work on behalf of the people. The kings need to remember that they serve the people and not the other way around. The reference to the moon can be viewed as a desire to see that the reminders to the King and princes about their tasks will no longer be needed. The King and princes will instinctively know to take care of the people.

Metaphorical translation – May the righteous man flourish in his days, and the abundance of peace, until the moon shall be needed no more.

Spiritual translation – The righteous man shall flourish so opulently, and the welfare of all shall grow in such abundance that the awareness of God, shining through every body and soul, shall tolerate no darkness of night upon the earth, and the moon shall be needed no more.

Verse sixteen

When the King takes care of his people as his number one priority, the LORD will lavish the King and nation with material blessings. This is the reward for being the King that the LORD wants the King to be.

May the border of grain in the land extend upon the top of the mountains; may its fruit rustle like Lebanon, but as for them may they blossom out of the city like the grass of the earth.

Verse twenty

David will have completed his goal when all the blessings listed in the Psalm have been obtained.

Then the prayers of David, the son of Jessie, will be at an end.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

